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RESEARCH ARTICLE.....!!!

SPECTROSCOPIC METHODS DEVELOPMENT FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF RIFAMPICIN AND OFLOXACIN

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ABSTRACT

The new, accurate, precise, reproducible and economic UV spectroscopic methods of rifampicin and ofloxacin have been developed for the simultaneous estimation. The method A-Dual wavelength, method B-Area under curve and method C-Absorption ratio method were developed by using JASCO double beam UV Spectrophotometer (model-V630). As simultaneous estimation was carried out, measurement of absorbance at two wavelengths 472 nm and 247 nm which shows λ_{max} values of rifampicin and ofloxacin respectively in distilled water. Rifampicin and ofloxacin shows linearity at selected wavelengths and obeys Beers law in the concentration range of 5-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with good correlation coefficient 0.992 and 0.998 respectively. For the area under curve the wavelength selected for rifampicin was from 434 nm to 506 nm and for ofloxacin 230 nm to 269 nm which gives peak area for rifampicin 6.7481 and for ofloxacin 15.5489. For the method C involved formation of isoabsorptive point at 287 nm.

KEYWORDS:

Absorbance Ratio Method,
Area under curve, Distilled
Water, Dual Wavelength.

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Rifampicin and ofloxacin are both drugs which are used in the treatment of tuberculosis and diarrhoea. Rifampicin is an intensely red solid, and the small fraction which reaches body fluids is known for imparting a harmless red-orange colour to the urine (and to a lesser extent, also sweat and tears) of users, for a few hours after a dose. Maximal concentrations in the blood are decreased by about a third when the antibiotic is taken with food¹.

Drug profile:

7*S*,9*E*,11*S*,12*R*,13*S*,14*R*,15*R*,16*R*,17*S*,18*S*,19*E*,21*Z*)-2,15,17,27,29-pentahydroxy-11-methoxy-3,7,12,14,16,18,22-heptamethyl-26-[(*E*)-[(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)imino]methyl]-6,23-dioxo-8,30-dioxo-24-azatetracyclo[23.3.1.1^{4,7}.0^{5,28}]trianta-1(28),2,4,9,19,21,25(29),26-octaen-13-yl acetate².

Chemical Structure:

Fig.1. Structure of rifampicin

Molecular formula:

C₄₃H₅₈N₄O₁₂³.

Molecular weight:

822.94 g/mol

Mechanism of action:

Rifampicin inhibits bacterial DNA-dependent RNA synthesis by inhibiting bacterial DNA dependent RNA polymerase. Crystal structure data and biochemical data indicate that rifampicin binds to RNA polymerase at a site adjacent to the RNA polymerase active center and blocks RNA synthesis by physically blocking the formation of the phosphodiester bond in the RNA backbone, preventing extension of RNA products beyond a length of 2-3 nucleotides ("steric-

occlusion" mechanism). Resistance to rifampicin arises from mutations that alter residues of the rifampicin binding site on RNA polymerase, resulting in decreased affinity for rifampicin. Resistant mutations map to the *rpoB* gene, encoding RNA polymerase beta subunit ⁴.

Drug profile:

Ofloxacin is a synthetic antibiotic of the fluoroquinolone drug class considered to be a second-generation fluoroquinolone. Ofloxacin is off-white to pale yellow crystalline powder. The molecule exists as a zwitterion at the pH conditions in the small intestine. The relative solubility characteristics of ofloxacin at room temperature, as defined by USP nomenclature, indicate that ofloxacin is considered to be soluble in aqueous solutions with pH between 2 and 5. It is sparingly to slightly soluble in aqueous solutions with pH 7 (solubility falls to 4 mg/mL) and freely soluble in aqueous solutions with pH above 9 ⁵. Ofloxacin has the potential to form stable coordination compounds with many metal ions. This in vitro chelation potential has the following formation order: $Fe^{+3} > Al^{+3} > Cu^{+2} > Ni^{+2} > Pb^{+2} > Zn^{+2} > Mg^{+2} > Ca^{+2} > Ba^{+2}$ ⁶.

Chemical structure:

(*RS*)-7-fluoro-2-methyl-6-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)-10-oxo-4-oxa-1-azatricyclo[7.3.1.0^{5,13}]trideca-5(13),6,8,11-tetraene-11-carboxylic acid ⁷.

Fig.2. Structure of ofloxacin

Molecular formula:

$C_{18}H_{20}FN_3O_4$ ⁸.

Molecular weight:

361.368 g/mol ⁹

Mechanism of action:

Ofloxacin is a broad-spectrum antibiotic that is active against both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. It functions by inhibiting DNA gyrase, a type II topoisomerase, and

topoisomerase IV, which is an enzyme necessary to separate (mostly in prokaryotes, in bacteria in particular) replicated DNA, thereby inhibiting bacterial cell division¹⁰.

There are so many methods described for the rifampicin and ofloxacin individually. However, there is no method reported for simultaneous estimation of both drugs¹¹.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

UV-visible double beam spectrophotometer Jasco model V-630 with spectral bandwidth of 2 nm, wavelength accuracy of ± 0.3 nm and a pair of 10 nm matched quartz cell was used. The API used as rifampicin, ofloxacin and the chemicals as distilled water was obtained from the institute P.D.V.V.P.F's. College of Pharmacy, Ahmednagar.

2.1 Preparation of Stock Solution:

Rifampicin 10 mg was weighed by using electronic balance (Model Shimadzu AUV-220D) and dissolves in a small amount of distilled water and then completely dissolved. After this the solution was adjusted to 100 ml in volumetric flask, So that the solution of 100 μg / ml was prepared. Like this the stock solution of ofloxacin were also prepared by dissolving 10 mg of drug into distilled water. For complete solubility the solution was sonicated for 2 min by using ultrasonic bath sonicator (model 5.5L150H) and then adjusted the volume upto 100 ml in volumetric flask.

2.2 Preparation of Sample:

From the stock solution of rifampicin and ofloxacin the standard solutions of both were prepared. For rifampicin the standards were prepared as 5-35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ by taking 0.5 ml of stock solution adjusted to 10 ml by using distilled water to prepare 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, 1 ml of stock solution was adjusted to 10 ml to get 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, 1.5 ml of stock solution was adjusted to 10 ml to get 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, 2 ml of stock solution was adjusted to 10 ml to get 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, 2.5 ml of stock solution was adjusted to 10 ml to get 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, 3 ml of stock solution was adjusted to 10 ml to get 30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ and 3.5 ml was adjusted to 10 ml to get 35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. After this the samples for ofloxacin were prepared as 5-35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. The dilutions were prepared as 0.5 ml from stock were taken and diluted upto 10 ml so as to get the solution of 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, 1 ml stock solution were adjusted to 10 ml to get the solution of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, 1.5 ml stock solution were taken and adjusted to 10 ml to get 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, 2 ml of stock solution were taken and adjusted to 10 ml to get 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, 2.5 ml of stock solution were taken and adjusted to 10 ml to get 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, 3 ml of stock solution were taken and adjusted to 10 ml to get 30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ and 3.5 ml of stock solution were taken and adjusted to 10 ml to get 35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$.

2.3 Measurement of Readings:

After the sample preparation readings were taken by using Jasco make double beam UV visible spectrophotometer. For the measurement of samples the blank readings were taken for correction of baseline. For measurement of λ_{\max} 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ samples of rifampicin and ofloxacin were taken. It shows the λ_{\max} of rifampicin and ofloxacin as 472 nm and 247 nm respectively. And the sample readings were taken by adjusting fixed wavelength at 472 nm and 247 nm.

2.4 Method A. Dual Wavelength Method:

If a sample contains two absorbing drug of each of which absorbs at the λ_{\max} of the other, it may be possible to determine both drugs by the technique of simultaneous equations.

$$C_x = \frac{A_2 a_{y1} - A_1 a_{y2}}{a_{x2} a_{y1} - a_{x1} a_{y2}} \quad (1)$$

$$C_y = \frac{A_1 a_{x2} - A_2 a_{x1}}{a_{x2} a_{y1} - a_{x1} a_{y2}} \quad (2)$$

2.5 Method B. Area under Curve:

For the simultaneous estimation using the area under curve method, suitable dilutions of the standard stock solutions (100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) of rifampicin and ofloxacin were prepared separately in distilled water. The solutions of drugs were scanned in the range of 200-800 nm. For area under curve method, the sampling wavelength ranges selected for estimation of rifampicin and ofloxacin were 434 nm to 506 nm (λ_1 - λ_2) and 230 nm to 269 nm (λ_3 - λ_4). Mixed standards were prepared and their area under the curve was measured at the selected wavelength ranges. Concentration of two drugs in mixed standard and the sample solution were calculated using equation (3) and equation (4).

$$C_x = \frac{A_2 a_{x2} - A_1 a_{y2}}{a_{x2} a_{y1} - a_{x1} a_{y2}} \quad (3)$$

$$C_y = \frac{A_2 - a_{x2} \times C_x}{a_{y2}} \quad (4)$$

2.6 Method C. Absorbance Ratio Method:

Absorbance ratio method is the uses of absorbance at two selected wavelengths; one of them is isoabsorptive point and second is λ_{\max} of any of the drugs. From the overlain spectra of the two drugs rifampicin and ofloxacin shows isoabsorptive point as 287 nm. The second wavelength is 247 nm which is the λ_{\max} of ofloxacin. Working standard solutions having the concentration range of 5-35 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ in distilled water. And the absorbance at isoabsorptive point and λ_{\max} of ofloxacin were taken.

The concentrations of two drugs were measured by using the equations (5) and (6).

$$C_x = \{(Q_m - Q_y) / (Q_x - Q_y)\} \times A_1 / ax_1 \quad (5)$$

$$C_y = \{(Q_m - Q_x) / (Q_y - Q_x)\} \times A_1 / ay_1 \quad (6)$$

Where A_1 and A_2 are absorbance's of mixture at 287 nm and 247 nm, ax_1 and ay_1 are absorptivities of rifampicin and ofloxacin at 247 nm, ax_2 and ay_2 are absorptivities of rifampicin and ofloxacin at 472 nm, $Q_m = A_2/A_1$, $Q_x = ax_2/ax_1$, $Q_y = ay_2/ay_1$.

3. Validation of Proposed Methods:

The proposed methods are validated according to the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines ¹².

3.1 Linearity:

The calibration curves were taken for both rifampicin and ofloxacin at 472 nm and 247 nm. Both the drug shows linearity and obeys Beer's Law in the concentration range of 5-30 µg/ml. The correlation coefficient of calibration curves were 0.992 and 0.998.

3.2 Precision:

Relative standard deviations (% R.S.D.) for intraday and inter day were calculated as precision study.

3.3 Limit of Detection:

The limit of detection was determined using the formula:

$$LOD = 3.3\sigma/S$$

Where, LOD is Limit of Detection, σ is the standard deviation, S is the slope of the calibration curve. LOD was found to be 0.1650 and 0.2766 for rifampicin and 0.7755 and 0.2426 for ofloxacin at the wavelength 472 nm and 247 nm.

3.4 Limit of Quantitation:

The limit of quantitation was determined using the formula:

$$LOQ = 10 \sigma/S$$

Where, LOQ is Limit of Quantitation, σ is the standard deviation, S is the slope of the calibration curve. LOQ was found to be 0.5000 and 0.7352 for rifampicin and 0.3500 and 0.7352 for ofloxacin at the wavelength 472 nm and 247 nm.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

The combination of rifampicin and ofloxacin used to treat two diseases, the patient suffering simultaneously. The present work gives a very simple, accurate and economic method for the

simultaneous estimation of both drugs. Both the drugs shows linearity at the wavelength selected 472 nm for rifampicin and 247 nm for ofloxacin and validated according to the ICH guidelines.

Table.1. Optimized method parameters for dual wavelength spectroscopy

Sr.No.	Method Parameters	Optimized Parameters
1.	Solvent	Distilled water
2.	Scanning Range	200 nm to 800 nm
3.	Scan Speed	Medium
4.	Analytical wavelength for determination of rifampicin	472 nm and 247 nm
5.	Analytical wavelength for determination of ofloxacin	472 nm and 247 nm

Table.2. Linearity

Rifam. (Conc.µg/ml)	Absorbance		Oflox. (Conc.µg/ml)	Absorbance	
	472 nm	287 nm		247 nm	287 nm
5	0.073	0.021	5	0.032	0.0233
10	0.1569	0.1296	10	0.4000	0.0907
.15	0.2481	0.2413	15	0.7202	0.1605
20	0.3383	0.3321	20	1.0501	0.2269
25	0.4155	0.4313	25	1.4009	0.2722
30	0.4909	0.5556	30	1.7857	0.3982
35	0.5373	0.6031	35	2.0325	0.4829

Table.3. Intraday Precision studies

Sr. No.	Conc. of drug ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance		SD		%RSD	
		Rifam.	Oflox.	Rifam.	Oflox.	Rifam.	Oflox.
1.	10 (n=3)	0.1568	0.4000	0.0001	0.00047	0.04	0.01
		0.1569	0.4001				
		0.1568	0.4000				
2.	15 (n=3)	0.2481	0.7201	0.00057	0.00057	0.02	0.01
		0.2480	0.7202				
		0.2481	0.7202				
3.	20 (n=3)	0.3382	1.0501	0.00047	0.00057	0.03	0.01
		0.3381	1.0500				
		0.3380	1.0501				

Limit: % RSD for area NMT 2.0%

Table.4. Inter day precision studies

Day	Conc. of drug ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance		SD		%RSD	
		Rifam.	Oflox.	Rifam.	Oflox.	Rifam.	Oflox.
1	10 (n=3)	0.1568	0.4001	0.0001	0.00047	0.04	0.01
		0.1568	0.4000				
		0.1569	0.4000				
2	15 (n=3)	0.2480	0.7202	0.00057	0.00057	0.02	0.01
		0.2481	0.7201				
		0.2480	0.7202				
3	20 (n=3)	0.3381	1.0500	0.00047	0.00057	0.03	0.01
		0.3382	1.0501				
		0.3380	1.0501				

Limit: % R.S.D. for area NMT 2.0%

Table.5. Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantification

Parameters	Rifampicin		Ofloxacin	
	At 472 nm	At 247 nm	At 472 nm	At 247 nm
LOD($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.1650	0.2766	0.7755	0.2426
LOQ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.5000	0.7352	0.3500	0.7352

Limit: % R.S.D. for area NMT 2.0%

Table.6. Regression Characteristics

Parameters	At 472 nm	At 247 nm
Beer's Law Range	5-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	5-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
Regression Equation ($y = mx + c$)	$y = 0.020x + 0.022$	$y = 0.068x + 0.032$
Slope (m)	0.02	0.068
Intercept (c)	0.022	0.032
Correlation Coefficient (R^2)	$R^2 = 0.992$	$R^2 = 0.998$

Fig.3. Spectra of rifampicin in distilled water

Fig.4. Spectra of ofloxacin in distilled water

Fig.5. Overlain absorption spectra of rifampicin and ofloxacin showing isoabsorptive point (287 nm) in distilled water

Fig.6. Area under curve of rifampicin

Fig.7. Area under curve of ofloxacin

Fig.8. Standard calibration plot of rifampicin in distilled water

Fig.9. Standard calibration plot of ofloxacin in distilled water

Table.7. Peak areas of rifampicin and ofloxacin by AUC

Area under curve for rifampicin			
Peak	Wavelength Range	Area	Area Ratio
Peak 1	434-506	6.7481	1
Peak 2	434-506	6.7481	1
Area under curve for ofloxacin			
Peak 1	230-269	15.5489	1
Peak 2	230-269	15.5489	1

CONCLUSION:

The new analytical methods were developed and validated according to ICH guidelines for the simultaneous analysis of rifampicin and ofloxacin.

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